

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Masoud****FIRST NAME: Ahmed****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied U.S. U.K. conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: Microsoft Word 365 on Windows 10

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) :

1. The Basics of Essay Writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-6)
3. Style Guide (EUCLID 2019, 25-26)
4. Latin Expressions and Abbreviations (EUCLID 2019, 56-61)
5. Some Rules of Thumb for Writing Papers (EUCLID 2019, 14-16)
6. Chicago Manual of Style (EUCLID 2019, 44-50)
7. American vs. British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-33)

THE IMPORTANCE OF INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

The English language became the global language for communication between people, especially in the topics of reading, writing, and educational materials; Despite its importance, it does not receive the same importance in developing countries, especially non-English speaking. I grew up in an Arabic country, but I studied the English language for many years, but I did not use it in my daily activities; the actual use of the English language began when I worked in a multinational company in a foreign country.

I was wondering about the benefits of re-studying international academic writing as a foundation course of EUCLID in the Ph.D. program. Is it not enough that the Ph.D. student studied at the master's level in the English language and submitted many assignments in English? I thought the best decision was to wait until the course began and to explore its content; after exploring the ACA-401D course, I realized that the writing stage is the most important stage of postgraduate studies, if not the most important one at all because it reflects the personality of the researcher, and it shows the reader the amount

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of effort that exerted in collecting the scientific material; Especially since the Ph.D. program depends mainly on the thesis which includes more than half of the credit hours required to achieve the degree.

2) THE CONCEPT OF INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING

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Academic writing is defined as formal, technical, and practical writing; so, it is formal and deviates from the usual conventions of speech, and moves away from non-academic terminology, where its aim to avoid personal feelings and personal views and focused on facts and ideas. It is the formal writing style of academic institutions; It is the formal method used by university students, postgraduate students, or university professors if they want to answer a specific academic question in articles or scientific theses, so it is writing that is characterized by a specific linguistic style and format consisting of specific tools, structures, and connotations. It is used in writing postgraduate theses, research, dissertations, reports, and scientific summaries. The author's background affects his/her academic writing, whether Standard British English (SBE) or Standard American English (SBA); As well as affects the manner of writing, grammar, dictation, conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics styles; which indicates the importance of studying the international academic writing to ensure the researcher uses correct academic writing style according to the accredited standards (EUCLID 2019, 27).

Euclid University wanted to shed light on the basics of international academic writing and the required skills to use it for postgraduate students through the ACA-401D course. The first period of the ACA-401D course focused on the basic principles of international academic writing and its different styles, the deep differences between them, and how to use them (EUCLID 2019, 14).

3) THE IMPORTANCE OF INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING

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International academic writing helps the student to write objectively, and to become familiar with accurate academic writing styles, how to write clearly, how to write rationally, concern for formal writing expressions, responsibility, density, and complexity, and how to write in a sound language strongly with no bias in views, teaching how to properly use academic and scientific tools and terminologies.

International academic writing contributes to sharpen the researcher's ability on the integrity of meanings and linguistic skills, teaching the correct use of linking tools, teaching the correct construction of sentences, teaching the correct construction of paragraphs, teaching how to correctly formulate questions and hypotheses, and how to formulate theses strongly while being keen on honor and integrity and being keen on avoidance the

plagiarism and showing the researcher's character in his/her academic writing clearly and correctly (EUCLID 2019, 4).

4) CHARACTERISTICS OF INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING

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International academic writing is characterized by accuracy and clarity in ideas and thoughtful and constructive scientific formulation. Accuracy must be met in every part of it, and the proposed academic ideas must be focused on understandable scientific facts, with the writing free from undue verbosity and redundancy.

International academic writing is characterized by its focus on scientific terminology related to the topic of research, as the scientific researcher must be proficient in terms and familiar with them and be able to use them in the right place and context for them, especially the need to differentiate between terms and conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics Standard British English (SBE) and Standard American English (SBA) (EUCLID 2019, 25).

5) REQUIREMENTS OF GOOD INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING

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International academic writing must provide many requirements, in order to be classified as sound academic writing that fulfills academic requirements, and the most important of these requirements is writing original content that is free from all kinds of plagiarism, whether intentionally or unintentionally (EUCLID 2019, 4).

International academic writing must provide strong research without misspellings. The researcher must be keen to present his/her research without any grammatical or spelling errors (EUCLID 2019, 34).

International academic writing must be met according to the most important rules and styles of well-known academic research and considering the specific terms and conditions of the university, in order to write properly that fulfills its goals, and in a correct and logical sequence, and with a good citation of all the references, books and journals that have been used in the writing (EUCLID 2019, 4).

6) BIBLIOGRAPHY STYLES

Citations and Bibliography of references in academic research are the most important steps that researchers must consider when preparing academic research, and it is the first point that the instructors' eyes fall upon when discussing academic research; in

order to refer honorably to the references that he/she used to get the information included in the research.

Academic research is one of the objective and practical methods; in order to get results related to a problem or phenomenon in one of the scientific fields, whether a theoretical or applied case. Academic integrity requires when getting data or information from a specific source that reference is referred to the source's author, to preserve the rights of others.

The researcher refers only to the information, or sources that serve the academic research. The documentation of references in academic research shows that the reader can refer to the source of the information; To get a greater amount in case of further expansion and get the original text (EUCLID 2019, 1).

There are many styles of Citations and Bibliography in academic research, such as the Harvard style, Oxford style, MLA style, APA style, and Turabian style (EUCLID 2019, 46).

EUCLID University recommends the Turabian style as the favorite style, Turabian Style was specially developed for students by Kate Turabian, of the University of Chicago; It is mainly used in too many disciplines (EUCLID 2019, 24).

Turabian Style is a standard style used to format academic writing; that provides two ways for citing information: The notes and bibliography method and the other method use quotes in the text and a reference checklist at the end (Pittsburgh).

7) CONCLUSION

This is my first assignment on my journey towards obtaining a Ph.D. in Conflict Management and Mediation (DMCR) degree. Period one of ACA-401D course was an excellent chance for me to sharpen my skills in academic writing, and citations.

The EUCLID ACA-401 coursepack, orientation templates and videos were a very useful tools to ease the understanding and preparation of the first response paper.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

Pittsburgh, University. "Home - Citation Styles: APA, MLA, Chicago, Turabian, IEEE - LibGuides at University of Pittsburgh." Home - LibGuides at University of Pittsburgh, University OF Pittsburgh. <https://pitt.libguides.com/citationhelp> (accessed Mar 25, 2021).

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.